

Information Needs and Information Usage of the Older Person Club's Members in Bangkok

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Abstract—This research aims to explore the information needs, information usages, and problems of information usage of the older people club's members in Dusit district, Bangkok. There are 12 clubs and 746 club's members in this district. The research results use for older person service in this district. Data is gathered from 252 club's members by using questionnaires. The quantitative approach uses in research by percentage, means and standard deviation. The results are as follows (1) The older people need Information for entertainment, occupation and academic in the field of short story, computer work, and religion and morality. (2) The participants use Information from various sources. (3) The Problem of information usage is their language skills because of the older people's literacy problem.

Keywords—Information Behavior, Older Person, Information Seeking.

I. INTRODUCTION

ACCORDING to the United Nations, the older population is those who are 60 years old and higher as defined in a term of 'elderly' or 'older person' [1]. Nowadays, the world is in ageing society and The Ministry of Social Development and Human Security in Thailand [2] reported that the proportion of older people is increased rapidly to 9.0 percent in 2000. Also, Ministry of interior, Department of Provincial Administration [3] summarized that the proportion of older people is increased to 12.67 percent in 2012. The proportion of older people in total population will increase to 14.0 percent in 2015, 19.8 per cent in 2025 and nearly 30 per cent by 2050. The population of older people will increase from the current 6.4 million to 9.0 million in 2015, 12.9 million in 2025 and exceed 20 million in 2050[4]. It is, therefore, expected that Thailand faces a rapidly growing population of older people and becomes ageing society recently.

Since society and economy have been changing, the older people hardly adapt to keep pace with the modern world. However, it is believed that most of the older people have greater knowledge and experience in life, culture, and society. The potential of older people is a powerful basis for future development. This enables society to increasingly enhance with the skills, experiences and wisdom of older people. Using information and information technology is the way to get knowledge. Older people can be fully integrated into society and assured a life of dignity and good health.

There are a lot of information forms such as printed materials, none printed materials and computerize materials, which can help the older people to adapt themselves to keep

up with various problems. The Information is necessary knowledge for their lives. The older people should get benefits of life-long education, and creating awareness. Overall, network and information technology are powerful tools to help them in communication and knowledge enrichment and information retrieval from anywhere and anytime so as to encourage older person's well-being where they can lead their life as an asset to the society. However, sometimes the older people have faced with problems in information needs, and information usage [5], [6]. Also, they need many kinds of information forms consisting of appropriate contents, packaging, data range and language [7].

In addition to the strategies of National Plan on the older people in Thailand, this research aims to explore information needs, information usages, and problems in information usage of the older people club's members, in case of Dusit District, in order to strengthen for the elderly community. Dusit district is one of the important districts in Bangkok province and there are 12 older people clubs and 746 club's members in this district.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents materials and methods used in this work. Section III presents the results of this experiment. Finally, in Section IV conclude the paper with future research.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Information Needs and the Older People

The word "Information needs" or "information wants" or "information demands" [8] is an individual or group's desire to locate and obtain information to satisfy a conscious or unconscious need. The objectives of studying information needs are:

1. The explanation of observed phenomena of information use or expressed need.
2. The prediction of instances of information uses.
3. The control and thereby improvement of the utilization of information manipulation of essentials conditions.

B. Materials and Methods

In this study, the sources are 746 older people club's member in Dusit district, Bangkok. The Yamane formula is used to calculate sample groups. The sample groups are selected randomly by stratified sampling system using Lottery method. From the calculation, there are 246 older people for sample. The duration of the study is from October 1 to 30, 2013.

The purpose of this survey research is to study information needs, information usage and to study problem in information

usage of the older people. Data gathering tool includes the questionnaires to find the percentage, means and standard deviation.

III. RESULTS OF THIS EXPERIMENT

The descriptive statistics was used to assess information needs and information usage of the older person club's members in Dusit Districts, Bangkok. It is shown as Tables I to III.

TABLE I
INFORMATION NEEDS OF THE OLDER PEOPLE CLUB'S MEMBERS IN BANGKOK

Items	\bar{X}	S.D.	Evaluation
I. Occupation	2.85	1.24	Moderate
1.1 Arts invention	2.54	1.21	Moderate
1.2 Artificial flowers making	3.52	1.14	High
1.3 Sewing	2.39	1.04	Low
1.4 Beauty salon	2.11	0.89	Low
1.5 Basketwork	3.27	0.93	Moderate
1.6 Computer work	3.56	0.99	High
1.7 Musical	2.52	1.28	Moderate
1.8 Singing	2.99	1.39	Moderate
1.9 Cooking	3.11	1.30	Moderate
1.10 Agriculture	2.51	1.20	Moderate
II. Entertainment	2.90	1.15	Moderate
2.1 Novel	2.57	1.06	Moderate
2.2 Short story	3.23	1.14	Moderate
III. Academic	2.86	1.28	Moderate
3.1 General information	2.50	1.12	Moderate
3.2 Philosophy	1.93	1.11	Low
3.3 Religion and morality	4.15	1.09	High
3.4 Social science	3.92	0.98	High
3.5 Language	2.68	1.06	Moderate
3.6 Science	2.87	1.29	Moderate
3.7 Technology	4.09	0.78	High
3.8 Arts	3.18	1.19	Moderate
3.9 Literature	3.22	1.15	Moderate
3.10 Geography and tourism	3.11	1.21	Moderate
Total	3.01	1.28	Moderate

From Table I, the result of information needs shown that the highest needs are computer work for occupation (\bar{x} =3.56, S.D. =0.99), short story for entertainment (\bar{x} =3.23, S.D. =1.14) and religion and morality (\bar{x} =4.15, S.D. = 1.09) for academic as respectively.

Fig. 1 The result of Information needs

TABLE II
INFORMATION SOURCES OF THE OLDER PEOPLE CLUB'S MEMBERS IN BANGKOK

Items	\bar{X}	S.D.	Evaluation
I. information Source	4.06	0.98	High
1.1 Friend /Companion	4.24	0.99	High
1.2 Mass media	4.13	0.93	High
1.3 Printed material	4.26	1.02	High
1.4 Community learning center	3.59	1.07	High
1.5 Their experience	4.09	0.68	High
II. Seeking Method	3.94	1.18	High
2.1 Made a conversation with their friend	4.15	0.82	High
2.2 Printed material searching i.e. book/ journal/ newspaper/pamphlet	4.40	0.58	High
2.3 Training	3.89	1.13	High
2.4 Community announcement	3.77	1.36	High
2.5 Their experiences	3.79	1.36	High
2.6 Sign board in community learning center	3.66	1.39	High
III. The way to get Information	3.45	1.02	High
3.1 Taking note	3.52	1.09	High
3.2 Requesting for free copy	3.56	0.95	High
3.3 Remember	3.28	0.98	Moderate
IV. format of Information usage	4.25	0.96	High
4.1 Books	4.15	0.93	High
4.2 Newspapers	4.44	0.89	Highest
4.3 Bulletin board in community learning center	4.15	0.82	High
4.4 Television program	4.71	0.59	Highest
4.5 Community announcement	3.80	1.19	High
V. Aim of Information usage	4.29	0.87	High
5.1 Follow up country situations	4.74	0.52	Highest
5.2 Entertainment	4.43	0.89	High
5.3 Health knowledge	4.06	0.71	High
5.4 leisure activity	3.93	1.02	High
Total	3.55	1.27	High

From Table II, the results of information sources presented that printed materials (\bar{x} =4.26, S.D. =1.02) was the highest and printed material searching i.e. book/journal/newspaper/pamphlet was the highest of seeking method (\bar{x} =4.40, S.D. =0.58). Also, requesting for free copy was the highest of the way to get information (\bar{x} = 3.56, S.D. = 0.95) and television programs was the highest of the format of information usage (\bar{x} = 4.71, S.D. =0.59). Moreover, follow up country situations was the highest of the aim of information usage (\bar{x} = 4.74, S.D. =0.52).

Fig. 2 The result of Information sources

TABLE III
THE PROBLEM OF INFORMATION USAGE OF THE OLDER PEOPLE CLUB'S MEMBERS IN BANGKOK

Items	\bar{X}	S.D.	Evaluation
1. Non-Literacy	1.86	1.17	Low
2. Unknown sources to find information	3.56	1.32	High
3. Language	4.67	0.61	Highest
4. Lack of knowledge about the technology and searching tool	3.36	1.20	Moderate
5 Do not know how to search	2.64	1.49	Moderate
6. Did not dare to ask others	3.35	1.19	Moderate
7. Lack of searching tool	3.80	1.08	High
8. Limited time	2.62	1.17	Moderate
9 Restrictions on health	2.50	1.35	Moderate
Total	3.19	1.41	Moderate

From Table III, the highest problem of information usage for the older people was language ($\bar{X} = 4.67$, S.D. = 0.61) and the lowest problem was non-literacy ($\bar{X} = 1.86$, S.D. = 1.17) as shown in Fig 3.

Fig. 3 The result of Information usages

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, it was divided the result by the research purpose into 3 parts:

A. Information Needs

The older people need information for entertainment the most. They need more information for occupation than for

academic. The contents of information are short story, computer work, and religion and morality respectively.

B. Information Usage

The way to get information used by the older people in highest level is requesting for free copy. Most of them use printed material especially newspapers for information source. They search information from printed material, and the aim of information usage is to follow country situations.

C. The Problem of Information Usage

The problem of information usage of the older people is their language skills because they have low education and they have illiteracy problems. Most of them are unable to read and communicate in foreign language.

However, the results above show the preliminary information to those responsible for the older people to provide information resources and searching tools for the older people and, in the future work, we are looking forward to researching about guidelines to promote learning and information services for older people in Bangkok, Thailand.

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